

Synthesis of 2'-(substituted)benzylidene hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and their antimicrobial activity

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Abstract : Several 2'-(substituted)benzylidene hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**5a-m**) have been synthesized by the condensation of 1-(*N*-aryl thioamido)thiocarbohydrazides (**3a-f**) and different aromatic aldehydes in benzene medium, followed by intramolecular cyclization of compounds (**4a-m**) in refluxing ethanol medium. The former in turn have been prepared by the reaction of aryl isothiocyanates (**2a-f**) and thiocarbohydrazide (**1**). Compounds (**5a-m**) on bromination with bromine in glacial acetic acid afforded dibromo derivatives (**6a-m**). The synthesized compounds were assayed for their antimicrobial activity against gram positive as well as gram negative micro-organisms.

Keywords : Synthesis, 1,3,4-thiadiazole, antimicrobial activity.

Sulphur and nitrogen containing heterocycles in general and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles in particular are shown to possess various biological activity¹. In view of our interest in heterocyclic synthesis, we are reporting the synthesis of 2-benzylidene hydrazino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles in the present communication.

Results and discussion

The parent compound thiocarbohydrazide (**1**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of aqueous hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) and carbon disulphide (0.01 mol) in H₂O.

A mixture of thiocarbohydrazide (**1**) (0.01 mol) and aryl isothiocyanates (**2a-f**) (0.01 mol) was refluxed in benzene medium when these were transformed into 1-(*N*-aryl thioamido)thiocarbohydrazides (**3a-f**). By condensing (**3a-f**) with different aromatic aldehydes in benzene medium afforded 1-(*N*-aryl thioamido)-5-(substituted)-benzylidene thiocarbohydrazides (**4a-m**). Compound (**4a**) was prepared by condensing (**3a**) with 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde. The reaction was further extended to prepare the compounds (**4b-m**) by condensing (**3a-f**) with benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde. On refluxing alone (**4a-m**) in ethanolic medium got intramolecularly cyclized with evolution of hydrogen sulphide gas. On pouring reaction mixture in water, the crystalline solids (**5a-m**) were isolated. The results are presented in Table 1. 2'-(Substituted)benzylidene hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-

thiadiazoles (**5a-m**) were found non-desulphurizable with hot alkaline plumbite solution indicating absence of >C=S group.

These compounds on bromination with bromine in glacial acetic acid afforded *N*-bromo-bromo-2'-(substituted)benzylidene hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**6a-m**). The results are presented in Table 2. The formation of products **3-6** has been shown in Scheme 1.

Antimicrobial activity :

The title compounds (**5a-m**) were screened for their antibacterial activity using cup-plate diffusion method. The bacterial organisms used included both gram positive and gram negative strains like *E. coli*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *P. vulgaris* and *Shigella flexneri*. Sensitivity plates were seeded with a bacterial inoculum of 1×10^6 CIU/ml and each well diameter (10 mm) was loaded with 0.1 ml of test compound solution (1000 µg/ml) in DMF. So that concentration of each test compounds was 100 µg/ml. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h using vernier calliper. Inhibition zone record of the compounds clearly indicated that **5a**, **5b**, **5c**, **5i** and **5m** were highly active against *E. coli*, **5a**, **5b**, **5f**, **5l** and **5m** were highly active against *B. subtilis* whereas moderately active against *P. vulgaris* and *Shigella flexneri*. Majority of the compounds were found to be resistant against *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. The results are presented in Table 3.

Scheme 1

Experimental

All melting points were recorded using hot paraffin bath and are uncorrected. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. IR spectra ($4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in nujol mull and as KBr pellets. PMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl_3 and $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ as solvents. Purity

of the compounds was checked on silica gel-G plates by TLC.

The parent compound thiocarbohydrazide was prepared by reacting the mixture of aqueous hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) and carbon disulphide (0.01 mol) in H_2O , maintaining the temperature below $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, m.p. $168\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Note

Table 1. Formation of 2'-(substituted)benzylidene-hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (5)

Entry	Compd.	R	R'	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
						Found/(Calcd.)			
						C	H	N	S
1	5a	<i>p</i> -Tolyl		80	169	59.01 (59.07)	4.60 (4.61)	21.47 (21.53)	9.80 (9.84)
2	5b	<i>p</i> -Tolyl		89	170	62.09 (62.13)	4.77 (4.85)	22.60 (22.65)	10.30 (10.35)
3	5c	<i>m</i> -Tolyl		72	165	61.89 (62.13)	4.47 (4.85)	22.55 (22.65)	9.97 (10.35)
4	5d	<i>o</i> -Tolyl		79	145	62.01 (62.13)	4.72 (4.85)	22.40 (22.65)	10.28 (10.35)
5	5e	Phenyl		74	169	60.85 (61.01)	4.42 (4.40)	23.68 (23.72)	10.80 (10.84)
6	5f	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl		72	171	54.65 (54.71)	3.44 (3.64)	21.18 (21.27)	9.65 (9.72)
7	5g	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl		84	175	54.32 (54.71)	3.55 (3.64)	21.32 (21.27)	9.56 (9.72)
8	5h	<i>p</i> -Tolyl		84	176	60.12 (60.17)	4.95 (5.01)	20.60 (20.64)	9.32 (9.43)
9	5i	<i>m</i> -Tolyl		74	170	59.97 (60.17)	5.07 (5.01)	20.45 (20.64)	9.28 (9.43)
10	5j	<i>o</i> -Tolyl		75	157	60.01 (60.17)	4.87 (5.01)	20.38 (20.64)	9.34 (9.43)
11	5k	Phenyl		78	174	58.94 (59.07)	4.53 (4.61)	21.44 (21.53)	9.72 (9.84)
12	5l	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl		76	169	53.38 (53.48)	3.84 (3.89)	19.32 (19.49)	8.76 (8.91)
13	5m	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl		87	175	53.32 (53.48)	3.74 (3.89)	19.42 (19.49)	8.82 (8.91)

Synthesis of 1-(*N-p*-tolyl thioamido)thiocarbohydrazide (3a) :

The compound 1-(*N-p*-tolyl thioamido)thiocarbohydrazide was prepared by refluxing the mixture of thiocarbohydrazide (1) (0.01 mol) and *p*-tolyl isothiocyanate (2a) (0.01 mol) in benzene (10 ml) medium for 2 h. On distilling off benzene, the product was isolated. It was

crystallized from benzene, yield 90%, m.p. 174 °C (Found : C, 42.29; H, 5.04; N, 27.40; S, 24.97. Calcd. for C₉H₁₃N₅S₂ : C, 42.35; H, 5.09; N, 27.45; S, 25.09%); ν_{\max}^3 3363 (NH), 1351 (C-N), 1211 (N-N), 1092 (C=S), 812 λcm^{-1} (*p*-substituted benzene); **3b** (80%), m.p. 155 °C; **3c** (78%), m.p. 168 °C; **3d** (84%), m.p. 170 °C; **3e** (85%), m.p. 166 °C; **3f** (87%), m.p. 170 °C.

Table 2. Formation of *N*-bromo-bromo-2'-(substituted)benzylidene hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**6**)

Entry	Compd.	R	R'	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
						Found/(Calcd.)			
						C	H	N	S
1	6a	<i>p</i> -Tolyl		84	194	48.52 (48.60)	3.48 (3.79)	17.38 (17.72)	8.02 (8.10)
2	6b	<i>p</i> -Tolyl		82	165	50.44 (50.65)	3.75 (3.95)	18.40 (18.46)	8.22 (8.44)
3	6b	<i>m</i> -Tolyl		80	152	50.60 (50.65)	3.98 (3.95)	18.44 (18.46)	8.38 (8.44)
4	6d	<i>o</i> -Tolyl		74	153	50.56 (50.65)	3.80 (3.95)	18.34 (18.46)	8.32 (8.44)
5	6c	Phenyl		81	170	49.22 (49.31)	3.42 (3.56)	19.11 (19.17)	8.65 (8.76)
6	6f	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl		79	167	44.97 (45.11)	2.87 (3.00)	17.42 (17.54)	7.94 (8.02)
7	6g	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl		86	170	45.04 (45.11)	3.04 (3.00)	17.35 (17.54)	7.85 (8.02)
8	6h	<i>p</i> -Tolyl		78	162	49.78 (49.87)	4.04 (4.15)	17.05 (17.11)	7.65 (7.82)
9	6i	<i>m</i> -Tolyl		82	156	49.78 (49.87)	4.17 (4.15)	17.04 (17.11)	7.74 (7.82)
10	6j	<i>o</i> -Tolyl		80	157	49.75 (49.87)	4.08 (4.15)	17.10 (17.11)	7.70 (7.82)
11	6k	Phenyl		78	170	48.42 (48.60)	3.53 (3.75)	17.53 (17.72)	8.08 (8.10)
12	6l	<i>m</i> -Chloro-phenyl		79	164	44.70 (44.75)	3.18 (3.26)	16.22 (16.31)	7.34 (7.45)
13	6m	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl		76	168	44.62 (44.75)	3.20 (3.26)	16.30 (16.31)	7.32 (7.45)

Synthesis of 1-(N-p-tolyl thioamido)-5-(2-hydroxy) benzylidene thiocarbohydrazide (4a) :

1-(*N-p*-Tolyl thioamido)-5-(2-hydroxy)benzylidene thiocarbohydrazide (**4a**) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of 1-(*N-p*-tolyl thioamido)thiocarbohydrazide (**3a**) (0.01 mol) and 2-hydroxy benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in benzene (10 ml) medium for 2 h. On completion of reaction and distilling off the solvent, a white solid powder

was obtained, it was crystallized from benzene, yield 87%, m.p. 145 °C (Found : C, 53.41; H, 4.65; N, 19.40; S, 17.80. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₇N₅S₂O : C, 53.48; H, 4.73; N, 19.49; S, 17.82%); ν_{\max} 3369 (OH), 3263 (NH), 1620 (C=N), 1319 (C-N), 1215 (N-N), 806 (*p*-substituted benzene), 744 cm^{-1} (C-S); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-}d_6)$ 10.66 (1H, s, OH), 9.87 (2H, s, NH, NH), 9.44 (2H, s, NH, NH), 8.38 (1H, s, Ar-CH=N), 6.99–7.47 (4H, m, Ar-H), 2.34 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃); **4b** (79%), m.p. 139 °C; **4c**

Note

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of 2'-(substituted)benzylidene hydrazino-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (5)

Entry	Compd.	Organisms				
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. flexneri</i>
1	5a	+++	++	+++	-	+
2	5b	+++	+	+++	+	-
3	5c	+++	-	++	-	++
4	5d	+	-	-	++	-
5	5e	-	-	+	-	-
6	5f	++	-	+++	-	++
7	5g	+	+	++	++	+
8	5h	++	+++	++	-	+
9	5i	+++	-	+	++	++
10	5j	-	++	++	+	-
11	5k	++	-	-	-	++
12	5l	+	-	+++	-	++
13	5m	+++	+	+++	++	++

Standard drug : Sterptomycin

(Diameter of inhibition zone in mm) (concentration 100 µg/ml)

(-) Resistant < 10.0 mm

(+) Slightly active > 10.0 to 15.0 mm

(++) Moderately active > 15.0 to 20.0 mm

(+++) Highly active > 25.0 mm

(74%), m.p. 130 °C; **4d** (77%), m.p. 130 °C; **4e** (81%), m.p. 145 °C; **4f** (84%), m.p. 135 °C; **4g** (87%), m.p. 138 °C; **4h** (77%), m.p. 143 °C; **4i** (72%), m.p. 134 °C; **4j** (80%), m.p. 131 °C; **4k** (83%), m.p. 141 °C; **4l** (85%), m.p. 138 °C; **4m** (89%), m.p. 140 °C.

Synthesis of 2'-(2-hydroxy) benzylidene hydrazino-5-p-tolyl amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (5a) :

A paste of 1-(*N-p*-tolyl thioamido)-5-(2'-hydroxy)-benzylidene thiocarbohydrazide (**4a**) was placed in (10 ml) ethanol and reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 4 h. The reaction proceeded with the evolution of hydrogen sulphide gas (tested with lead acetate paper). The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into water, a white solid was precipitated. It was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (70%). It was found non-desulphurizable on boiling with alkaline plumbite solution indicating absence of >C=S group, and identified as 2'-(2-hydroxy) benzylidene hydrazino-5-*p*-tolyl amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**5a**), yield 80%, m.p. 169 °C (Found : C, 59.01; H, 4.60; N, 21.47; S, 9.80. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₅N₅SO : C, 59.07; H, 4.61; N, 21.53; S, 9.84%); ν_{\max} 3410 (OH), 3325 (NH), 1618 (C=N), 1278 (C-N), 1199 (N-N), 810 (*p*-substituted benzene), 744 λcm^{-1} (C-S); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-}d_6)$ 11.36 (1H, s, Ar-OH), 9.2-9.4 (2H, s, NH, NH), 8.57 (1H, s, Ar-CH=N), 6.97-7.68 (8H, m, Ar-

H), 2.37 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃).

Synthesis of N-bromo-bromo-2'-(2-hydroxy)-benzylidene hydrazino-5-p-tolylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (6a) :

To the solution of 2'-(2-hydroxy)benzylidene hydrazino-5-*p*-tolylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**5a**) (0.01 mol) in acetic acid, was added bromine in glacial acetic acid with vigorous shaking. Within half an hour the reaction mixture solidified. On pouring the reaction mixture into little crushed ice, the granular solid was obtained. This product was crystallized from aqueous ethanol (70%). The compound was identified as *N*-bromo-bromo-2'-(2-hydroxy)benzylidene hydrazino-5-*p*-tolylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**6a**), yield 84%, m.p. 194 °C (Found : C, 48.52; H, 3.48; N, 17.38; S, 8.02. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₅N₅SOBr₂ : C, 48.60; H, 3.79; N, 17.72; S, 8.10%); ν_{\max} 3429 (OH), 3327 (NH), 1619 (C=N), 1278 (C-N), 1201 (N-N), 810 (*p*-substituted benzene), 745 λcm^{-1} (C-S); $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-}d_6)$ 10.72 (1H, s, OH), 9.25 (2H, bs, NH, NH), 6.90-7.76 (8H, m, Ar-H), 2.37 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃).

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